

Technological indicators for water-smartness

Deliverable 2.1

Technological indicators for water-smartness

D2.1 of Work package 2

Summary

Deliverable 2.1 – Technological indicators for water-smartness - presents the work completed under task 2.1 in WP2, developing a set of technical indicators for assessing water smartness within the B-WaterSmart framework. The deliverable included an in-depth literature review of previous and on-going work on defining technical indicators suitable for assessing sustainability and in extension water smartness across different contexts. The literature review was then combined with feedback from each of the six Living Labs (LL) in B-WaterSmart broadening the focus with input from water utilities, water boards and municipalities with very different infrastructures (both existing and planned), challenges and possibilities. This review with each of the LL ensured alignment with the varying current situation and challenges faced in each of the LLs spread out across Europe. Technical indicators need to be seen in the context of those challenges faced by the water sector, in which they will be used both for benchmarking present states and future development scenarios.

Coupled with the B-WaterSmart framework strategic objectives and assessment criteria and building on previously conducted work in the Deliverable 6.1 of the B-WaterSmart project, which delivered a definition for water smartness, deliverable 2.1 proposes a set of metrics and indicators for Water-Smart societies. These indicators will be a building block for the assessment of Water smartness in the B-WaterSmart project and feed into a holistic framework that will be developed in T6.2.

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Table of contents

List of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
Executive summary	7
1 Introduction	8
2 Water-Smart society concepts	11
2.1 Sustainable water management	11
2.2 Integrated water resource management	11
2.3 Circular economy and society	12
2.4 Smart cities and water smartness	13
3 Indicators for Smart Cities and Urban Water Systems	14
3.1 Existing frameworks	14
3.2 Existing indicators	15
4 Methodology	18
4.1 Definition of good metrics and indicators	18
4.2 Description of Living Labs within the B-WaterSmart project	20
4.3 Applied Concepts and methodologies in selection of metrics and in D2.1	22
5 The proposed indicators in Work package 2	24
5.1 B-WaterSmart taxonomy	24
5.2 Selected Technical indicators	26
6 Outlook	32
7 References	33

List of Figures

Figure 1. Hybrid approach of technical indicator collection.....	19
Figure 2. Living Labs of the B-WaterSmart project	20

List of Tables

Table 1. The list of dimensions, strategic objectives, and assessment criteria of the B-WaterSmart framework.....	25
Table 2 List of technical metrics and indicators proposed in D2.1. The alphanumeric list in the “metric” column links to the assessment criteria as defined in table 2 above	30

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AC	Assessment Criteria
CBF	City Blueprint Framework
CCRO	Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis
CE	Circular Economy
EBC	European Benchmarking Co-operation
Eco.	Economic
Env.	Environmental
EIGs	External Impact Generators
EU	European Union
Gov.	Governance
IIGs	Identification of Internal impact Generators
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
IVI	Infrastructure Value Index
M	Milestone
NBS	Nature Based Solution
NGO	Non-Governmental organizational
No.	Number
IT	Information Technology
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LL	Living Lab
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
SO	Strategic Objective
Soc	Social
Tech.	Technical
TRUST	TRansition to sustainable Urban Systems of Tomorrow
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations

UWCS	Urban Water Cycle Services
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
ZMN	Zero Emission Neighbourhoods

Executive summary

Deliverable 2.1 provides an overview of the technical indicators which can be used to assess the technical aspects of the work undertaken in each of the six Living Labs in the B-WaterSmart project. To support a water-smartness framework with strategic objectives and assessment criteria, the deliverable 2.1 proposes a set of metrics and indicators for a water-smart society. The results also build upon the previously conducted work in the Deliverable 6.1 of the B-WaterSmart project, which delivers a project definition for a water smartness. The purpose of the indicators is to address, measure and benchmark the technical aspects within the already defined B-WaterSmart project framework. A hybrid approach consisting of an extensive literature review and inputs asked for and delivered by the six Living Labs (LL) of the project, was applied to select, and define technical indicators based on the "Strategic objectives" and "Assessment Criteria" defined in earlier phases of the project. Metrics and indicators were chosen to address the challenges of each of the Living Labs and provide quantitative assessments for these challenges. This review with each of the LL ensured alignment with the varying current situation and challenges faced in each of the LLs spread out across Europe. Technical indicators need to be seen in the context of those challenges faced by the water sector, in which they will be used both for benchmarking present states and future development scenarios.

1 Introduction

The urban water sector in Europe is faced with serious challenges over the coming decades; such as extreme events caused by climate change, the growing population and aging water infrastructure (Gralepois, 2020; Mikovits et al., 2018; Stavenhagen et al., 2018). This started already more than a decade ago, as already in the year 2007, a minimum 11% of the population and 17% of the European territory had been affected by the water scarcity and climate change effects (Stavenhagen et al., 2018). The occurrence of extreme flooding events reported across Europe in countries such as the UK, France, Spain, and Romania have steadily increased in the period of 1990s-2010s (Gralepois, 2020) and in Germany in summer 2021 (Fekete et al., 2021). Combined more than 700 fatalities have been caused by extreme flooding around Europe since 2000. Sea level rise and increased river flows endanger an almost 15 % of the total global population with an increased risk of flooding (Koop and van Leeuwen, 2017). This is the case in some cities including almost all worlds' megacities (Ligtvoet and Hilderink, 2014). Extreme rainfall events and in consequence triggered pluvial flooding may become even more severe due to global warming (Jongman et al., 2014). As urban surfaces are often sealed (and will increasingly be so due to urbanization) and green areas are limited, the impact of pluvial flooding in urban areas is even more intensified (Mikovits et al., 2018). Also, the increased water demand in developing and developed countries would lead to a shortage of freshwater by 2030 of almost 40 % (2030 WRG, 2009). Global water demand is projected to increase by 55% between 2000 and 2050 and, by 2050, over 40% of the global population are likely to be living in river basins under severe water stress (OECD, 2015).

Urban authorities face challenges of water pollution from the management as well as the governance perspectives. Water quality in urban waterways, reuse of stormwater and rainwater harvesting are relying on fit-for-purpose water quality of the reused water. A challenge that is growing in light of climate change. Climate change lays bare these existing urban water vulnerabilities regarding flooding, water scarcity and water pollution (Gralepois, 2020; Koop and van Leeuwen, 2017; Reese and Gawel, 2018; van Leeuwen et al., 2012). Although water scarcity is usually caused by the lack of available water sources, it can also be a result of a mismatch between the available water resources and water demand, which depends on the current population of an urban area and may be aggravated by future migration trends in the area (Stavenhagen et al., 2018). Pollution caused by combined sewer overflows and stormwater systems is expected to rise due to extreme rainfall events (Nilsen et al., 2011). Rapid urbanization will lead to extra stresses on the adjacent environment. For instance, wastewater treatment is still not common and widely spread in parts of Asia and Africa and differences in quantity and quality can be seen even in Europe, and as a result the nutrient emissions are expected to increase to double or triple in almost 40 years. This phenomenon will enhance eutrophication, biodiversity loss, endanger the drinking water quality, wherever ground- and surface water is used, and aquaculture (Ligtvoet and Hilderink, 2014).

The above-mentioned challenges in urban areas around the world makes policymakers looking for short-term as well as long-term solutions to address these changes. In this regard, a benchmarking system of urban sustainability indicators has proven to be a proper means to assess technical, social, and environmental impacts of different aspects of infrastructures, governance and policies (Koop and van Leeuwen, 2015; van Leeuwen et al., 2012).

The UN report 2021 groups current methodologies and approaches for the valuation of water and water-related services, which can be viewed from five interrelated perspectives:

- valuing water sources, in situ water resources and ecosystems.
- valuing water infrastructure for water storage, use, reuse, or supply augmentation.
- valuing water services, mainly drinking water, sanitation, and related human health aspects.
- valuing water as an input to production and socio-economic activity, such as food and agriculture, energy and industry, business, and employment.
- other sociocultural values of water, including recreational, cultural, and spiritual attributes (Ugarelli et al., 2021).

The B-WaterSmart project objectives and criteria established for the assessment framework are in line with these perspectives and have been classified into similar related categories of social, economic, technical, economic, and governance. These objectives and criteria formed the basis for the proposed final definition of a water-smart society (Ugarelli et al., 2021) based on the feedback from the six Living Labs of the B-WaterSmart project:

“Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses, to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society, to boost value creation around water, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure”.

The purpose of this Deliverable 2.1 is to introduce a comprehensive and applicable list of technical indicators for benchmarking in line with the defined water smartness, based on literature, experience and the abilities of the Living Labs (LLs). The Living Labs (LL) within this project were formed around a water utility or municipality either as a problem owner or end-user solution and a research partner which work together on a local, municipal, or metropolitan scale.

The herein described set of urban water technical indicators were derived from the strategic urban water management objectives and the assessment criteria defined in deliverable 6.1 (Ugarelli et al., 2021) and then determining how they can be best represented by performance indicators and measured by well-defined metrics. Consultation was undertaken with the Living Labs experts and stakeholders to consider how the indicators may align with their practice needs (Renouf et al., 2017).

In fulfilling these objectives this report is structured in the following way:

Section 2 highlights the features that should characterize a water-smart society providing a preliminary definition based on a comprehensive literature review of key concepts and frameworks related to sustainable water management, integrated water management, smart cities.

Section 3 provides some experiences in literature regarding the set of indicators defined and tested in smart cities and the urban water field.

Section 4 introduces the Living Labs acting within the context of B-WaterSmart project together with the challenges they face and the technical solutions each of Living Labs are exploring.

Section 5 presents the methodology applied to deliver the set of indicators. First the characteristics of proper metrics and indicators based on previous experiences in the project as well as literature is presented.

In section 6 the selected list of metrics and indicators are described and discussed.

Finally, Section 7 presents key conclusions and next steps.

2 Water-Smart society concepts

Section 2 highlights the features that should characterize a water-smart society providing a preliminary definition based on existing project results (Ugarelli et al., 2021), a comprehensive literature review of key concepts and frameworks related to sustainable water management, integrated water resource management, circular economy and society and smart cities.

2.1 Sustainable water management

Implementation of water-smartness in society should be oriented to sustainability, *i.e.*, sustainability should be the goal for the society and being water-smart can provide better ways to achieve or to maintain sustainability. However, there is a high variety of existing definitions and views about sustainability (Heinrichs et al., 2016). Therefore as a point of departure, the sustainable water management concept developed in FP7 TRUST (TRansition to sustainable Urban Systems of Tomorrow) project (e.g., Nottarp-Heim et al., 2015) was chosen, that focuses on opportunities for strategic long-term transitions towards sustainability in urban water services will be applied and further evolved in B-WaterSmart.

According to Brattebø *et al.* (2013), "Sustainability in urban water cycle services (UWCS) is met when the quality of assets and governance of the systems is sufficient to actively secure the water sector's necessary contributions to social, environmental and economic sustainability in the urban system as a whole". In Alegre (2012) the needed contributions are linked to urban social, environmental, and economic development, in "a way that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" thus replicating the Brundtland Commission. Sustainability assessment of UWCS should be transparent, valid, and holistic, and must include the dimensions of social, environmental, economic, asset and governance sustainability.

2.2 Integrated water resource management

Uncertainties arising from climate and environmental crisis in cities require new approaches towards efficient and resilient management of the urban water cycle. These must respond to challenges resulting from the combination of population growth and aged water infrastructures, shifts in social priorities and public policies, a new demand on governance and emerging technologies, including natural systems, information technology (IT), and small-scale modular units. Adapting to these dynamic settings implies the need for an integrated and integrative perspective. This is amongst other highlighted in the new Adaptation Strategy from the European Union, which acknowledges that sustainable water management requires closer cooperation between adaptation action and water management authorities, and transformational changes across all sectors (European Commission, 2021).

Urban water cycle management approaches should not only emphasise sustainable water use, but also protect the environment and enhance biodiversity. The water sensitive urban design approach describes the process that promotes a greater sensitivity to water in the urban water cycle as an alternative to

traditional water management approaches (Artioli *et al.*, 2017). By promoting harmony between natural and urban processes, it seeks to restore the natural water cycle in the urban context, give access to different water sources, protect water bodies, and reduce the risks associated with extreme weather events. Water is recognized as an essential asset that must be valued and integrated not only into the urban scale but also at the watershed landscape scale.

The water-energy-food nexus has achieved prominence as one of the possible frameworks to assess this integrated model to investigate urban complexity. The nexus sets an imperative for integrated management and policymaking, centring on the potential trade-offs and complementarities between interdependent water, energy, and food systems (MacGrane *et al.*, 2019). In this respect water-smartness implies a significant shift of public policies configurations on matters such as the water supply, food security and energy efficiency to city dwellers and users. On the one hand, cities are sites of water, food and energy distribution, consumption and to a lesser extent, production, and reuse.

Water resources are not circumscribed to the area where they are consumed. They spread across territories, through river basin hydrographic networks and ecosystems, including rivers, lakes, water reservoirs, and aquifers. Water ecosystem services associated with the hydrological cycle, and affected by the climate, land cover and management should be considered part of the circular economy concept with an integrated view across the entire water cycle.

2.3 Circular economy and society

Transformation towards a circular economy (CE) has become an important issue in environmental management and it is a core part in the European Green Deal. In general terms, CE can be defined as "*a system where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimised.*" (European Commission, 2015). The New Circular Economy Action Plan emphasizes that this requires radical rethinking and exploring new ways of ensuring long-term wellbeing for all, where cities, as engines for economic development, can drive the agenda forward (Eurocities, 2020). Moreover, the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities that was officially launched in June 2020, emphasizing "*The transition to a circular economy*" as one of six environmental objectives towards 2030 (European Union, 2020).

The influential Water and Circular Economy white paper by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation emphasizes the need to optimize design of waste externalities, resource yields and resource extraction from the water system, while maximizing regeneration of natural capital by reducing consumption and non-consuming use of water (EMF, 2018). Some methods to prevent waste are already applied, summarized as the so-called:

- 2Rs: reduction, meaning preventing wastewater generation in the first place by the reduction of water usage and pollution reduction at source, and reuse, considering reuse of wastewater as an alternative source of water supply.

- 3Rs: including recovery or reclamation of water from wastewater for potable or non-potable usage.
- 4Rs: adding recovery of resources as nutrients and energy from water-based waste (Smol et al., 2020).

Williams (2019) suggests that not only looping, but also regenerating and adapting are fundamental to the delivery of the circular processes in cities. Regeneration refers to preservation of natural capital and essential ecosystem services, *e.g.*, through incorporation of green and blue infrastructure. Adaptation involves planning and design to enable the adaptation and renewal of existing infrastructure with minimal resource wastage, *e.g.*, through flexible, modular systems and meanwhile spaces.

2.4 Smart cities and water smartness

The smart city concept contains the notion of cities testing and implementing innovative, sustainable, and integrated solutions to become greener, more efficient, and better places (EUROCITY, Smart cities & digital transformation – Eurocities). A smart city' is often seen to use digital technologies to engage more effectively and actively with its citizens. Enhancing the city performance and wellbeing of the citizens, reduce operational costs and the city resource consumption, generate new business opportunities and increase the attractiveness of the city (<https://www.etsi.org/technologies/smart-cities>). Smart cities may be perceived as the original platform economies that can now (with the foundation blocks of ICT, connectivity, and data) benefit from copying models used by digital platform businesses to bring actors together in new ways (Wilson, 2019). However, when smart cities become too smart, there is a danger that it might lead to public choice constraints, *i.e.*, no alternatives to smart solutions. Other problems include cyber security issues due to cyber-attacks on critical infrastructures and problems with deployment (Singh *et al.*, 2020), as well as issues with data availability, and cost of investment.

A comprehensive understanding of the smart city integrates the water cycle intrinsically and explicitly, as a resource, as potentiator of quality of life and as a potential risk source that needs to be managed (Ahvenniemi *et al.* 2017, Allam and Newman, 2018; Anthopoulos, 2017; Bibri *et al.* 2017; Buck and While, 2017). Water-smartness needs to be aligned with the comprehensive smart city concept and water management needs to foster multisector approaches to gain visibility to other city stakeholders thus raising opportunities for common actions with common benefits.

3 Indicators for Smart Cities and Urban Water Systems

Section 3 provides some experience in literature regarding the set of indicators defined and tested within the smart cities and urban water field.

3.1 Existing frameworks

As mentioned earlier, what motivates scientists and policymakers to approach efficient, quick, and resilient management of the urban water cycle are the increasing level of uncertainties due to climate change and environmental crisis in last decades. Stakeholders work in the areas related to urban water try to address current urban challenges caused mainly by population growth, aging water infrastructures, the new requirements on governance and innovative technologies, such as natural systems and information technology (IT). Adapting to these dynamic settings calls for integrated and comprehensive context in the urban scale.

In order to overcome the abovementioned challenges and to move toward smart and sustainable cities, the related authorities must adapt the current accessible resources and develop strategies to meet their specific targets (Pellicer et al., 2013). In this regard, a key performance indicators system on urban sustainable development is proved to be a reliable instrument to assess technical, socio-economic, and environmental impacts of current aspects of infrastructures and administrative decisions. Based on these indicators, urban officials and policymakers would be capable of distinguishing the current problems and identifying areas that can be improved by better managerial decisions as well as technical solutions. The indicators also allow city officials to monitor outcomes of long-term planned investments and to evaluate their impacts and to develop relevant future strategies (Picioara et al., 2018).

There are several indicators' systems under different names in the literature, such as "green city", "eco-city", "sustainable city", "low-carbon city", "digital city" or "smart city" (Eremia et al., 2017). In a research study by Giffender et al., (2007), the medium-size cities and their initiatives for development have been studied and the assessment metric ranking based on different ranges of indicators have been developed for the pre-identified dimensions of a smart city. In another research (Caragliu et al., 2011), seven layers and levels within the concept of smart cities have been developed: City Layer, Green City Layer, Interconnection Layer, Instrumentation Layer, Integration Layer, Open Application Layer, and Innovation Layer. In some research work (e.g., Qi and Ba, 2016), the Analytic Hierarchy Process method has been applied to evaluate several small cities in China, on the basis of infrastructure level, public supporting system, etc. Finally, Boselli et al. (2021) implemented the multi-criteria decision-making model to weigh some factors to support the innovation of a smart mobility in Milan, Italy.

Focusing on urban water smartness and the sustainable evolution in this regard, it is necessary to assure a proper management of urban water, such as resources, network resilience, energy efficiency and access to good quality of water. It is also of great importance to impellent strategies to avoid risks such as health-related risks or flood hazard (Picioara et al., 2018). All the reviewed visions of urban water

management contain objectives for protecting water resources, which include (i) protection of surface and groundwater resources through sustainable use, (ii) protection of water quality through the management of pollutant discharges, and (iii) restoration of natural hydrological flows.

As stated by van Leeuwen et al. (2012) some of the indicators designed in the context of sustainable cities include the European common indicators (European Commission, 2001) the sustainable cities index (Australian Conservation Foundation 2010; Forum for the future 2010), the European green city index (Stelzner, 2009). It is stated elsewhere that these sets of indicator frameworks are very generic and do not necessarily address the urban water cycle. It is worth noting that, in general, some indicators may have the purpose of assessing some aspects globally for a region, country, etc. or for a strategic decision level, e.g., regulation. Other indicators need to be more detailed or specific, depending on the level of assessment (e.g., tactical, or operational) for management purposes of a system or subsystem and hence it is very important to consider this factor when selecting a list of indicators. Also, the European Benchmarking Co-operation (EBC 2010) contains some frameworks for drinking water and wastewater. This set of mainly quantitative indicators is very useful although it lacks the broader context of cities, sustainability, and governance (van Leeuwen et al., 2012).

A set city-specific water indices have been developed and applied by van Leeuwen (2013) and Koop and van Leeuwen (2015). The so-called City Blueprint Framework (CBF) captures many aspects of urban water security and specifically to measure the extent to which cities implement the principles of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) and thus to compare their resilience to social, economic, and environmental pressures as 'water wise' or 'water sensitive' cities, as conceived in the IWRM perspective. The index is performance based, and present ideal blueprint of urban water management and measures how close cities come to this ideal.

3.2 Existing indicators

One of the most important aspects of sustainable urban water management is **water security**. Indicators of urban water security are included in several composite indicators, such as the Asian Development Bank's urban water security index, which forms part of the national water security rankings (ADB, 2020). However, the data included have been designed as averages for all urban areas across a country and are not likely to be salient for decision makers in a municipal- level.

According to the United Nations University (2013), the water security definition can be stated as:

"The capacity of a city to safeguard sustainable access to adequate quantities of acceptable quality water to sustain livelihoods, human wellbeing, and socio-economic development for its inhabitants and to ensure reasonable protection against water-borne pollution and water-related damage, and to establish and preserve healthy ecosystems in the city and its catchment"

Based on this definition four categories of urban water security can be expressed as below (Jensen and Wu, 2018):

1. Resource availability: refers to availability of water sources in each area, e.g., surface and groundwater, desalination, reclaimed water, etc. Regarding the sustainability and the smartness this factor should consider diversity, quality, and reuse of the resources.
2. Access: refers to the water accessibility for different application such as for drinking, for industrial as well as agricultural uses. This factor considers perspectives such as the treatment capacity, network coverage and affordability to use water.
3. Risk: refers to probable risks due to flood risk and the health-related accidents.
4. Capacity: refers to managing the capacity of water supply and water demand.

Another important objective to approach the smart water societies is the **water resource management**. The sustainable management of water resources has been a long-term goal of regional water resource management, which can be partly achieved by allocation of available surface and ground waters to several urban water functions. A sustainable water resource management includes **supply and resource efficiency** and ensuring the **storage capacity** for different sectors of urban, industry and agriculture. Another crucial features of resource management are sustainable management of water, energy, and nutrient resources. Resource efficiency, defined as the efficient use of water-related resources, includes energy to transport and treat water, and the nutrients mobilized in water. Within the context of urban water smartness, the resource efficiency covers aspects such as efficient use of water, and the efficient use and management of water-related energy and nutrients. Energy use and nutrient are important aspects in the framework of food-water-energy nexus and resource recovery. In this regard, the water-related energy refers to energy used to pump, treat, and dispose of water, and cooling and heating purposes. **Nutrient efficiency** represents the proportion of nutrient loads (nitrogen and phosphorous) in wastewater and stormwater that can be recovered and utilized. Its quantification will require an urban nitrogen and phosphorous balance as an overlay of the water mass balance (Renouf et al., 2017).

Another important aspect of sustainable urban water management are the **resilience and reliability** of urban water infrastructure. In general, what seems best for an urban water infrastructure is a long-term planning which sets the life cycle of the asset considering the aspect of sustained and sustainable service provision. In this regard, the infrastructure value index (IVI), can be seen as a powerful tool for long-term planning of linear and vertical assets. IVI is the ratio between the current value of an infrastructure and its replacement cost and can be assessed in several different ways (Alegre et al., 2014). It has however several weaknesses, mainly connected to the inability to consider future service evolution and the difficulty to calibrate and validate (Bruaset, 2019).

The reliability of a system is generally defined as its probability to operate successfully (Jung et al. 2014) and is defined as “the degree to which the system minimises level of service failure frequency over its design life when subject to standard loading” (Butler et al., 2017). Other definition is mentioned in Makropoulos et al. (2018) as the asset performance within its design life and during periods where the

expected level of service is met. Another proper explanation of the word can be mentioned as; the probability that an item will perform a required function, under stated conditions, for a stated period (Smith, 2017).

As cited in Butler et al., (2017) and according to Butler et al. (2014), resilience can be defined as “the degree to which the system minimises level of service failure magnitude and duration over its design life when subject to exceptional conditions”; essentially. In other words, resilience-based systems aim to overcome failure and ensure that the system is safe enough in unexpected situations (Makropoulos et al., 2018). As mentioned in Cañizares (2021) and according to UN-Habitat (2017), in policymakers’ vision, resilience is seen as a proper response to shocks and stresses and as a legal objective for urban transformation, which may overlap sustainability in some cases. In order to evaluate how resilience urban water services are, the system boundaries and the disturbances of the system should be determined. This is a challenging task as the urban water system can have different scales depending on the end-users such as households, technologies, and ecosystems (Johannessen & Wamsler, 2017).

4 Methodology

4.1 Definition of good metrics and indicators

In this section, first the characteristics of good indicators and metrics based on the literature and earlier reports in B-WaterSmart project (Ugarelli et al., 2021), and how this relates to the selection of the technical indicators in section 5 are presented. Indicators are defined within the context of a metric and according to (Jensen and Wu, 2018) shall follow the following characteristics:

Indicators proposed within any context need to be credible (Lehtonen, 2015). They should be scientifically reliable and technically robust and can capture changes in the phenomenon of interest accurately. Data must already exist to fulfil the indicators verification, or it must be realistic to collect the data within time and budget constraints and from a trusted source to do that. The construction of the proposed indicators and should be transparent and consistent.

Indicators also need legitimacy to be accepted by stakeholders. Legitimacy refers to the function of the indicator development process. It is stated elsewhere in the literature the importance of stakeholder involvement in supporting the selection of indicators. In this regard the process of indicator development needs to be collaborative and cover a broad and comprehensive range of perspectives (Damkjaer and Taylor, 2017; Norman et al., 2013).

According to literature, the indicators degree of importance and significance, influence the chance of it to be picked up in policymaking. This factor may be seen as a matter of awareness as some indicators do not select nor be implemented since decision-makers are not aware of them (Lehtonen, 2015). Also, some indicators may be neglected as not seen to be relevant to policy goals, are difficult to understand and discuss, or not relevant to the appropriate level of policy. An example of this situation may occur between, local policymakers and national policymakers to perceive an indicator data the same importance (Jensen and Wu, 2018; Norman et al., 2013). As already mentioned, the purpose and the level of application of indicators are different and important to consider when selecting them. Some indicators may have the purpose of assessing some aspects of a situation for a region or in a broader scale of a continent for a strategic decision level, e.g., regulation, policymaking. Other indicators need to provide more detailed information of the criteria, depending on the level of assessment (e.g., tactical, or operational) for management purposes of a system or subsystem.

The definition of the metrics to be included in the B-WaterSmart framework will also comply with the requirements listed below (Ugarelli et al., 2021).

- be relevant for the strategic objectives of the Living Labs.
- fit in the predefined assessment criteria.
- be clearly defined, with a concise meaning.
- be reasonably achievable (which mainly depends on the related variables).
- be auditable.

- be as universal as possible and provide a measure which is independent from the conditions of the LL.
- be simple and easy to understand.
- be quantifiable to provide an objective measurement of the service, avoiding any personal or subjective appraisal (best use of already collected data should be made).
- include information on the data quality of the variables and instructions on how to assess it.

The choice of metrics will be a balance between on the one hand strategic objectives and criteria of LLs as stated in Deliverable 1.7 (Schmuck & Wencki, 2021), and on the other hand data availability. As a result, some performance metrics may turn out to be site-specific while other metrics are more generic. The balance proposed is about 75% generic and 25% site-specific performance metrics. For each criterion, two to three metrics per LL, with at least one metric that is measured in all LL, are aimed at.

When looking at the list of metrics later to assess them, the following criteria shall be fulfilled:

- every assessment metric provides information significantly different from the other metrics in the framework.
- definitions of the assessment metrics are unequivocal (this requirement is made extensive to its variables).
- only metrics which are deemed essential for effective performance evaluation are established.

To collect meaningful indicators and metrics a hybrid approach (see Figure 4) is used based on the literature in chapter 3 and input and review from the LLs. The collected metrics in this report are mainly based on the Living Labs general and specific technical requirement to handle their current challenges and to fulfil the future proposed smart water aspects.

Figure 1. Hybrid approach of technical indicator collection

4.2 Description of Living Labs within the B-WaterSmart project

There are six Living Labs within the B-WaterSmart project context. These sites are located across Europe in Norway, Germany, Belgium, Italy, Spain, and Portugal. An overview of the six Living Labs (LLs) across Europe is presented in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..**

Figure 2. Living Labs of the B-WaterSmart project

Within each Living Labs there is one pilot area with tests and experiments based on the challenges which the site faces. The Living Labs sites and main actors in the B-WaterSmart project were chosen based on four main criteria:

1. Broad coverage and complementarity of scales, users, sectors, challenges, and geographical spread across Europe.
2. High ambitions by local end-user / problem-owner towards water-smartness.
3. Coastal location: Given that 40% of EU population lives in coastal regions, project results will have a high level of relevance, and a high replication and transferability potential; and the common denominator of a coastal setting will facilitate mutual learning and cross-pollination among the LLs.
4. Solution providers were picked based on their solution's performance related to the LL challenges, and their potential for interoperability, replicability, transferability, and market uptake (also beyond coastal Europe).

The current statuses of each of these action labs including the present condition and challenges together with technical aspects of water smartness task are described in the following sections.

Alicante

Alicante and its metropolitan area (1125 km²) currently face water scarcity challenges. Water reuse in the area is currently limited, due to excessive content of salinity and nitrates. Presently, 25% of regenerated water in Rincón de León WWTP cannot be reused although there is a need to reuse 100% of the water regeneration capacity to alleviate pressure on agricultural and municipal uses. This requires infrastructure investments, and thus a need to raise awareness among the stakeholders of the benefits of increased water reuse.

The Alicante action lab in Spain is mainly looking to boosting water reuse at municipal level; turning a wastewater treatment plant into a bio-factory: recover minerals, nutrients, salts, and energy.

Bodø

Bodø, Norway is at the start of a large re-urbanization process, which involves relocating the airport and building a new city district at the former airport site.

This living lab mainly focus on three challenges for small to medium size cities in northern regions: i) improve resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way, given the small scale, especially concerning biogas production from sludge; ii) reduce energy consumption and improve the quality of the wastewater stream, by improving wastewater quality, using improved infiltration detection technologies coupled with leak detection technologies, in an integrated system; iii) reducing the use of de-icing and anti-slip agents in the city centre to significantly improve air quality and reduce soil & water pollution. The alternative de-icing will use excess heat from biogas utilization for electricity production in combination with sea water

East Frisia

In this lab drinking water from groundwater resources has been delivered to private, industrial, and agricultural customers (and treating wastewater in ~50% of the area). The area faces climate change causing hot and dry summer periods with increasing water demands especially in agriculture. Furthermore, pollution due to livestock farming compromises usability of water resources for drinking water purposes.

The Living Lab looking to a sectional decentralized water supply strategy using untapped local water resources, e.g., reuse of treated process water instead of drinking water in dairy & food industry, e.g., wastewater reuse for other industries, recirculation of water in intense livestock farming, tap urban groundwater as service water resource, improve water demand forecast via smart metering.

The design and implementation of a pilot plant to treat vapor condensates and milk/whey permeate for reuse in the dairy industry is the focus in this Living Lab. The treatment train includes a combined biological treatment followed by physical treatment (ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis).

Flanders

As Belgium ranks 23rd globally in the 2019 National Water Stress Ranking, and there is a high sense of urgency – at all levels – this Living Lab's main objective is to work towards more robust water systems. Several concepts are currently explored by the case partners, including alternative water resources and ASR storage buffer for drinking water (De Watergroep), and stormwater retention and reuse for agriculture.

Technical work within this living labs are mainly to establish regional circularity in the water system: alternative water resources for drinking water supply, secure irrigation by interaction with the urban reuse cycle. At the first demonstration site two pilots will be running to investigate the production of drinking water from wastewater effluent and from off-spec raw water respectively.

Lisbon

Lisbon (Portugal) has a smart management strategy for all key areas of urban development. Awarded European Green Capital 2020, the city aims at providing high quality of life for an increasing population and growing economy, whilst tackling climate change challenges based on a green-blue problem-solving infrastructure. For water efficiency, Lisbon has been implementing new standards in municipal buildings, but no auditing/certification mechanism is in place.

The technical proposed tasks for this living lab consist of improving the city's water-smartness as green areas' sustainable increase enabler; recent and forthcoming national & EU regulation calling for sound guidelines/tools for risk management; national plans for CE and carbon-neutrality, promoting water (and related energy and phosphorus) use efficiency, safe and sustainable non-potable urban water reuse and demonstrating the potential and safety of potable water reuse in the beverage industry, namely in craft beer production.

Venice

Venice (Italy) and the nearby lagoon zones are sensitive areas, with 1 million citizens and 42 million tourists per year. A regional/national plan for lagoon protection has introduced technologies and NBS solutions to foster reuse of treated municipal wastewater at the industrial level, but several barriers have hindered its implementation.

The proposed technical tasks for this LL consist of directly and indirectly promote the application of i) boosting the water reuse at multiple level (industrial/urban and agricultural) of the available treated municipal wastewater; ii) fostering the best practices of nutrient/energy recovery from wastewater treatment and sludge management in a logic of low environmental impact and economic sustainability; iii) developing Integrated Evaluation Digital Strategic Platform, to support concerted governance/stakeholders' evaluations for objective, replicable and updatable sustainability assessments (LCA/LCC/Carbon footprint) of reuse/recovery opportunities.

4.3 Applied Concepts and methodologies in selection of metrics and in D2.1

In this section the main concepts and methodologies applied in the work used to select metrics and indicators of this deliverable are explained.

The first methodology in this regard comes from a study by Jensen and Wu (2018) in which they pilot and test the development of UWSI (Urban Water Security Indicators) implementing the Process Analysis Method (PAM) for indicator selection. Based on a cause-effect-analysis, this approach has been originally designed by Tahir and Darton (2010) to develop a comprehensive set of indicators of a pre-defined system and to measure sustainability performance of the system such as river basin sustainability. The PAM approach provides a general understanding of large and complicated systems through intensive literature review and stakeholder engagement.

The process of generating the urban water indicators as stated in Jensen & Wu (2018) can be briefly expressed as Identification of Internal impact Generators (IIGs) which are activities within the urban area, (e.g., water governance and regulation), as well as External Impact Generators (EIGs), generators outside the system boundary, (e.g., global climate change). These factors affect the urban water system in terms of water resources availability, risks and resilience or institutional. These Impacts pose consequences for stakeholders and these consequences are then described by the indicators and measured by the chosen metrics.

Application of PAM for measuring metrics within a pilot of a case study is through the following steps:

- 1) Conducting an in-depth review of the urban water system of each case study, assessing the status of water resources, water-caused risks and hazards and the water-related issues pose by climate change.
- 2) Determining the system boundary in spatial and temporal scales (Bell and Morse, 2008) where the spatial scale refers to the physical size of the system e.g., the geographical scale of a city and the covered inhabitants. The temporal scale, on the other hand, should be broad enough to ensure the water security within a feasible period of time.
- 3) Assessment of the indicators, which within this approach shall cover consequences of the Impacts for its probable receiver.
- 4) Assessment of the indicators, which within this approach shall cover consequences of the Impacts for its probable receiver.
- 5) Finally, the selected set of indicators as well as relevant measurements and data should be verified through assessment by the relevant stakeholders e.g., government officials, utility managers, NGOs, etc in the urban water domain. The metrics come from this methodology in Deliverable includes **“resources”**, **“access”** and **“risk”**.

The next set of selected indicators are based on the work by Leeuwen et al., (2012), who evaluate the sustainability situation in cities, within the context of planning process for Integrated Urban Water Management (IUWM) (Philip et al. 2011) refers to as the city blueprint. The city blueprint approach is similar to the one of the European green city index (2009), with a closer look on the sustainability of the urban water cycle (Siemens 2011). City blueprints enable the IUWM of cities to be compared amongst other cities to address the challenges may arise in future.

The approach is an exploratory approach with the aim to develop a method as practical, simple, transparent, easy to understand for decision-makers as well as the public and enables the quick assessment of sustainability of IUWM of a city. The City Blueprint contains a set of 24 indicators. The selected indicators were based on the following criteria (a) simply accessed, (b) easily understood, (c) relevant timewise relevant, (d) trustworthy and consistent, (e) credible, and accurate, (f) proposed while the end-user in mind. The indicators are design to assess and analyse the water issues within an urban water system and the related stakeholders within the water management framework (Philip et al. 2011). The metrics based on this concept include **“water system leakages”**, **“energy efficiency”**, **“nutrient recovery”**.

5 The proposed indicators in Work package 2

Within the B-WaterSmart project, some definitions and interrelations between the Framework's dimension, strategic objective, assessment criteria and metrics are provided to facilitate the collaboration in developing the content of the Framework and its future use. The following section (6.1) mainly contains the finding of B-WaterSmart deliverable 6.1 (Ugarelli et al., 2021).

5.1 B-WaterSmart taxonomy

The B-WaterSmart assessment taxonomy has five dimensions, reflecting the dimensions of sustainability transitions: *i.* social, *ii.* environmental, *iii.* economic, *iv.* technical and *v.* governance.

The **social dimension** is reflecting the ambition of a water-smart society in contributing to life-enhancing relations within the affected communities. It includes the enhancement of quality of life, in terms of health and safety, socioeconomic impact creation, employment, equitable distribution among users and realization of cultural values, but also the active engagement of citizens as fundamental actors in the transition process. Assessment criteria and metrics related to the strategic objectives under the social dimension will be aligned with the work performed under WP5.

The **environmental dimension** includes all direct impacts of solutions implementation on the environment as well as preservation and protection of the environment under different scenarios of change (including climate changes). Environment can refer to urban environment, natural environment, ecosystems: the different characterizations will be expressed through the adoption of adequate assessment criteria. The main objectives in the environmental dimension are to ensure an efficient use of resources and avoid undesirable environmental impacts. Assessment criteria and metrics related to the strategic objectives under the environmental dimension will be aligned with the impact that activities performed in the LLs might have to the environment and it is expected to be related with the work performed mainly in WP2, WP3 and in part inspired by WP4.

The **economic dimension** checks the affordability, the ability to promote circular business models and develop new markets around the value of water. Economic strategic objectives, assessment criteria and metrics will be aligned with the work performed under WP4 to ensure the B-WaterSmart Framework can assist in measuring the level of circular economy opportunities implementation and feasibility.

The **technical dimension** reflects the level of performance of a given innovative solution in providing expected functions, to be defined in the context of the project objectives and which will characterize the list of selected assessment criteria and metrics. The criteria and the metrics will have to facilitate the assessment of level of progress in achieving technical strategic objectives, which, at this stage are identified as the ability to transform water systems from being passive to being pro-active and adaptive and the ability to shorten the water distribution and use chains. Assessment criteria and metrics related to the strategic objectives under the technical dimension will be aligned with the work performed under WP2 and partially 3.

The **governance dimension** reflects the fundamental role of good governance to enable the transition process towards water-smart societies, by way of reliable management, stakeholder's engagement, cohesive policies, and processes, as well as sufficient awareness, statutory compliance, coordination,

and financial viability. Assessment criteria and metrics related to the strategic objectives under the governance dimension will be aligned with the work performed under WP4 and WP5.

Each dimension is characterized with a list of selected strategic objectives. Each objective is specified by assessment criteria as points of view that allow for the assessment of the objectives. Each criterion in turn is described with a set of indicators or metrics which will serve to assess the distance from a set target.

A brief description of each of these terminologies is presented as:

1. Dimensions describe the value-components within the concept and definition of water-smart society.
2. Strategic objectives are the end goals that the LLs aim to achieve. Objectives must be clear and concise, as well as ambitious, feasible and compatible, and take into account the ultimate goal for of achieving the "water smart society" vision. The set of strategic objectives is both comprehensive (incorporating all relevant aspects of a water-smart society) and long term (*i.e.*, 10, 20 or 50 years).
3. Criteria are points of view that allow for the assessment of the objectives. For each criterion, metrics must be selected for targets to be set, and for further monitoring of the results.
4. Metrics are the specific parameters or functions used to assess criteria quantitatively or qualitatively; metrics can be indicators, indices, or levels.

A list of updated Strategic Objectives and Assessment Criteria of the project is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The list of dimensions, strategic objectives, and assessment criteria of the B-WaterSmart framework

No.	Strategic Objective (SO)	Soc.	Env.	Econ.	Tech.	Gov.	Assessment criteria (AC)
#.1	A. Ensuring water for all relevant uses	++	+	+	+	+	A.1 Safe and secure fit-for-purpose water provision
							A.2 Accessibility and equity (for people and for other uses)
							A.3 Financial viability
#.2	B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society	+	++	+	+		B.1 Safeguarded water ecosystems
							B.2 Enhanced ecosystem services to society
							B.3 Resource efficiency
#.3				++	+	+	C.1 Circular policy making

Now we explain the metrics, indicators, sub-indicators, the reason to select on each and the measurement methodologies applied to each.

The metric **“resource”** together with the indicator **“availability”** are the first input from this methodology. The metric and indicator aim to address the provision of water for all relevant users in urban, agriculture and industry sectors. In this regard three sub-indicators have been defined. The **“water resource availability”** measures the availability of main sources of water (e.g., surface water and groundwater) in each region based on geographical and environmental situation together with other relevant and realistic sources (e.g., desalinated, and reclaimed water) considering the renewability of the source. The sub-indicator **“water storage capacity”** measures the volume of water store in reservoirs based on the daily average demand in the area and aims to ensure the availability of the required amount of water for different purposes. The last sub-indicator in this regard, **“current drinking water consumption”**, measures domestic water consumption per capita as this is an important factor help the urban water authorities to have a realistic view of the consumption patterns in the area and the related impacts on the treatment plants as well as on the reservoir’s capacity.

As mentioned earlier in this report, the flooding and its consequences have been a common problem in world as well as Europe in the last decades. In this regard, the metric **“risk”** has been selected to address the public safety in terms of probable urban floods and its potential threats to inhabitants. **“Flooding risks”** has been chosen as the general indicator here described further by two sub-indicators. The **“flood frequency indicator”** aims to measure the number of extreme floods occurred in each region per year which may ends in some hazardous events and consequences. The **“flood fatalities”**, on the other hand, is the ratio of fatal cases to the inhabitants of a region under study.

Provision of safe and secure water for different end-users shall fulfil the very important aspect of water quality. In order to address this important feature, the metric **“quality”** together with the indicator of **“raw water quality”** are defined. The indicator aims to measure the proportion of samples that meets the required guideline standards. The guidelines are different based on the final usage of water, for example in case water uses for drinking the EU drinking water guidelines shall meet and if the water uses in a reclamation process and for cooling purposes in industry, it shall meet the required physical and chemical criteria.

Access to water is another important factor in ensuring the water for different purposes of human need and has some aspects within it. Given **“access”** as a metric and **“capacity”** as the main indicators, two sub-indicators can be defined to fulfil the different features in this regard. The sub-indicators **“water supply capacity”** aims to measure the proportion of the available treatment plants in the covered area (considering the non-renewable water) to average demand of water on a daily basis. The **“water systems coverage”**, on the other hand measure the percentage of the inhabitants with access to both a treated tap water and a sanitary collection system. Another factor which might be useful to mention here is the cost of the covering distance. Although cost by itself is not a technical factor but considering the cost posed to an urban municipality due to provide access to non-covered people, the distance of

non-covered area and the cost to provide coverage is an indicator to provide as a financial one and from technical point of view.

Safeguarding ecosystem is another important topic which studied within the WP2. In this regard two matrices have been defined which described in this section. Another “risk” metric has been defined in this regard to describe the probable consequences to public and the environment and hence produce the two indicators: “**public health risk**” and “**environmental risks**”. The “public health risk” aims to assess the related water contaminants by the help of sub-indicator “**water contamination incident**” and can be measure as the number of incidents posed by water contaminants by the utilities. The “environmental risk”, on the other hand, is another important sub-indicator measures the number of events and discharges from the collection systems. This is an important factor to keep in mind especially with areas with heavy rainfall events and the probable sewer overflows. Resource efficiency or the so called “doing more with less”, is another important area to be addresses to benefit both the ecosystem and the society. The metric “**resource and distribution efficiency**” and the indicators “**diversity**” and “**efficiency**” have been defend in this regard. The indicator “**diversity**” which has been further addressed by the sub-indicator of “**diversity of water usage and reuse**” tries to address the water usage efficiency by different users and sectors both in suing water in an efficient and suitable way and to reuse the water by different means of reclamation etc. The indicator “efficiency”, on the other hand, covers two sub-indicators of “**transport efficiency**” and “**water system leakages**”. “**transport efficiency**” refers to the overall condition of the collection systems and the percentage of water which may be lost in the system due to exfiltration from the sewage systems and to the beneath groundwater. The “**water system leakages**” addresses an important issue of the distribution systems within the urban areas and cause the percentage of water lost in the distribution system.

The “**energy**” used for different urban water purposes such as, different steps in treatment plants in pumping water is another important metric considered. The indicator “efficiency” together with sub-indicators of “**energy efficiency**” and “**energy recovery**” have been defined in this regard. The “energy efficiency” measures the total energy derived from renewable sources and which is used as a total energy consumption in an urban area. The “**energy recovery**” refers to the techniques and methods used to treat wastewater and to recover energy e.g., in term of biogas production. Talking about this fact, the cost-benefit analysis of the method uses, and the end products should always be considered to discuss it with the relevant authorities and stakeholders.

To address the resource recovery in a smart society, the metric “**efficiency**” is defined. The selected indicator in this category is the “**use of resources and the produced material**”. The indicator considers the wastewater collected by means of collection systems in urban area and consist of two sub-indicators, “nutrient recovery” which refers to the percentage of wastewater treated in wastewater treatment plants to recover nutrients such as phosphate and the “sewage sludge quality” which measures the percentage of sludge which can be used as agricultural fertilizers given that the required chemical and biological criteria are met.

The last set of indicators have been defined to address the resilience infrastructures and the required changes to approach that. “Adaptivity” is the first metric in this context and present “service sustainability” as the measuring indicator. The sub-indicator “cost recovery” tries to address the ratio of the operating expenditure to operating revenue of an asset. The next metric is “value” which together with the indicator “infrastructure value index” tries to measure the current condition for an asset calculating the ration of infrastructure current value and the cost of its replacement. “Reliability” is the metric defined to assess the asset performance in different condition within its lifetime. The two indicators in this framework “supply reliability” and “frequentist reliability”. The “supply reliability” describes the water supply interruptions per year which may cause to some problems. “frequentist reliability” on the other hand describes the number of probable failure of assets in a year which afterward require repair or re-instalment.

Table 2 List of technical metrics and indicators proposed in D2.1. The alphanumeric list in the “metric” column links to the assessment criteria as defined in table 2 above

Metric	Indicator	Sub-indicators	Indicators description	Unit
A1) Resource ¹²³⁸	Availability	Water resource availability	Renewable surface water + renewable groundwater + imported water, desalinated water, reclaimed water (as applicable) per year per capita	m ³ /year/cap
		Water storage capacity	Total volume of water stored in water reservoirs (m3) expressed as a multiple of average daily demand	No. days
		Current drinking water consumption	Domestic water consumption per capita	L/ day
A1) Risk ¹	Flooding risks	Flood frequency indicator	Number of serious flooding events per year, which causes serious infrastructure damages.	No / year.
		Flood fatalities	Fatalities due to floods per year	No of fatalities / region inhabitants
A2) Quality ¹²⁴⁸	Raw water quality		Proportion of samples meeting the required water quality standard	%
A3) Access ¹⁴	Capacity (diversity)	Water supply capacity	Total water treatment capacity×(1-NRW) per day/average demand per day	%
		Water systems coverage	Percentage of population with access to tap water supply	%
			Percentage of population with access to collection system	%
B1) Services Risk ¹	Public health risk	Water contamination incidents	Number of water contamination incidents recorded by the utility e.g., “Boil water advisory” per year	%
	Environmental risk		Number of events and volume of discharge from collection system	Volume of sewage spilt as a % of the volume of sewage transported.
B3) Resource and distribution efficiency ¹²³⁴⁸	Diversity	Diversity of water usage, water reuse	Water usage efficiency in different sectors	%
	Efficiency	Transport efficiency	water lost in the urban collection system	%
		Water system leakages	Percentage of water lost in the distribution system	%
B3) Energy ²⁵	Efficiency	Energy efficiency	Percentage of total energy derived from renewable sources, as a share of city’s total energy consumption	%
		Energy recovery	Percentage of wastewater treated with techniques to generate and recover energy	%

Table 2 List of technical metrics and indicators proposed in D2.1. The alphanumeric list in the “metric” column links to the assessment criteria as defined in table 2 above

Metric	Indicator	Sub-indicators	Indicators description	Unit
C3) Efficiency²³	Reused materials	Nutrient recovery	Percentage of wastewater treated with techniques to recover nutrients, especially phosphate	%
		Sewage sludge quality	Percentage of sewage sludge that can be safely used in agriculture based on organic/inorganic micro- contaminants	%
D1) Value¹⁶⁷	Service sustainability	cost recovery of water utilities	Operating expenditure / operating revenue	Ratio
	Infrastructure Value index		Infrastructure current value / infrastructure true replacement cost	%
D3) Reliability⁸	supply reliability		Days of supply outage / year	Ratio
	Frequentist reliability		Number of incidents (requiring repair) / year	Ratio

¹ Jensen & Wu., 2018

² Renouf et al., 2017

³ Van Leuween & Frijns., 2012

⁴ Essential Services Commission., 2012

⁵ Picioroaga et al., 2018

⁶ Alegre et al., 2014

⁷ Bruaset., 2019

⁸ Gibberd., 2017

6 Outlook

Deliverable 2.1 proposes some metrics and indicators for Water-Smart society based on an extensive literature review of the current urban water related indicators and the B-WaterSmart framework strategic objectives and assessment criteria. The water-smart society concepts and framework is the result of the Deliverable 6.1 and were further developed in this report, which resulted in the proposed technical indicators. The general and specific challenges and needs of each of LLs of the B-WaterSmart project together with the provided feedback from their side were considered in revising the list.

In the next steps, WP6 will provide a user-friendly indicators-based framework to assess water-smartness. The technical indicators provided within this deliverable will be used together with input provided by WP4 and WP5 to ensure that the framework will offer a holistic overview including the technical (WP2), circular economy (WP4) and governance and social aspects (WP5), in addition to the indicators on resources availability, use/reuse efficiency and related risks.

It is also planned to develop a holistic framework in T6.2 to assess water-smartness at different scales of operational environments (local, city, metropolitan, regional, or national). Based on T6.1, evaluation framework will be developed qualitative and quantitative indicators to assess water-smartness, including technical (WP2), circular economy (WP4) and governance and social aspects (WP5). The framework will support the steps of diagnosis (baseline), priority setting, assessment of alternatives scenarios, and monitoring of performances through the list of selected indicators.

As a routine of the project and in order to be confident that the development of solutions in WP2 is fully aligned with the LLs, there will be a structured and iterative exchange between WP1 and these WPs about mutual information needs.

7 References

- 2030 WRG., 2009. Charting Our Water Future: Economic frameworks to inform decision-making. 2030 Water Resources Group.
- ADB, 2020. Asian Water Development Outlook 2020: Advancing Water Security across Asia and the Pacific. Asian Development Bank, Manila, Philippines. <https://doi.org/10.22617/SGP200412-2>
- Ahvenniemi, H., Huovila, A., Pinto-Seppä, I., Airaksinen, M., 2017. What are the differences between sustainable and smart cities? *Cities* 60(A): 234-245
- Australian Conservation Foundation., 2010. Sustainable Cities Index. Ranking Australia's 20 largest cities in 2010. Melbourne, Australia
- Allam, Z., Newman, P., 2018. Redefining the Smart City: Culture, Metabolism and Governance. *Smart Cities* 2018, 1, 4-25.
- Alegre, H., Coelho, S.T., 2012. Infrastructure Asset Management of Urban Water Systems. Chapter 3 of "Water Supply System Analysis", ed. Avi Ostfeld (ISBN 978-953-51-0889-4). Open access at: www.intechopen.com/books/water-supply-system-analysis-selected-topics
- Alegre, H., Covas, DIC., Coelho, ST., Almeida, MC., Cardoso, MA., 2012. An integrated approach for infrastructure asset management of urban water systems. *Water Asset Management International* 8.2. 10-14
- Alegre, H., Vitorino, D., Coelho, S., 2014. Infrastructure Value Index: A Powerful Modelling Tool for Combined Long-term Planning of Linear and Vertical Assets. *Procedia Eng.*, 16th Water Distribution System Analysis Conference, WDSA2014 89, 1428–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.469>
- Anthopoulos, L. 2017. Smart utopia VS smart reality: Learning by experience from 10 smart city cases. *Cities* 63: 128-148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2016.10.005>.
- Artioli, F., Acuto, M., McArthur, J., 2017. The water-energy-food nexus: An integration agenda and implications for urban governance. *Political Geography* 61: 215-223
- Bibri, SE., Krogstie, J., 2017. Smart Sustainable Cities of the Future: An Extensive Interdisciplinary Literature Review. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 31: 183-212
- Boselli, R., Cesarini, M., Mercorio, F., Mezzanzanica, M., 2021. Applying the AHP to Smart Mobility Services: A Case Study. Presented at the Special Session on Knowledge Discovery meets Information Systems: Applications of Big Data Analytics and BI - methodologies, techniques and tools, pp. 354–361.
- Brattebø, H., Alegre, H., Cabrera, E., Marques, RC., Hein, A., Cruz, CO., 2013. A Master Framework for UWCS Sustainability. D 31.1 TRUST project, January 2013
- Bruaset, S., 2019. Long term sustainable asset management for water infrastructure (PhD). NTNU, Trondheim, Norway.
- Buck, NT., While, A., 2017. Competitive urbanism and the limits to smart city innovation: The UK Future Cities initiative. *Urban Studies* 54(2): 501–519
- Butler, D., R. Farmani., G. Fu., S. Ward., K. Diao., M. Astaraiie-Imani., 2014. A New Approach to Urban Water Management: Safe and SuRe. 16th Conference on Water Distribution System Analysis, WDSA 2014. Elsevier, Bari, Italy.

- Butler, D., Ward, S., Sweetapple, C., Astaraie-Imani, M., Diao, K., Farmani, R., Fu, G., 2017. Reliable, resilient and sustainable water management: the Safe & SuRe approach: Reliable, Resilient, and Sustainable Water Management. *Glob. Chall.* 1, 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.1010>
- Cañizares, J.C., Copeland, S.M., Doorn, N., 2021. Making Sense of Resilience. *Sustainability* 13, 8538. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158538>
- Caragliu, A., Del Bo, C., Nijkamp, P., 2011. Smart Cities in Europe. *J. Urban Technol.* 18, 65–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2011.601117>
- Cordeiro, S., Rosa, M., 2020. Water-smart solution for Lisbon, summary and timeline (T2.4), B-WaterSmart.
- Damkjaer, S., Taylor, R., 2017. The measurement of water scarcity: Defining a meaningful indicator. *Ambio* 46, 513–531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-017-0912-z>
- EBC, 2010. European Benchmarking Co-operation. Learning from international best practices. 2010 water & wastewater benchmark. Leiderdorp, The Netherlands
- Eremia, M., Toma, L., Sanduleac, M., 2017. The Smart City Concept in the 21st Century. *Procedia Eng.*, 10th International Conference Interdisciplinarity in Engineering, INTER-ENG 2016, 6-7 October 2016, Tirgu Mures, Romania 181, 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.02.357>
- EMF, 2018. Water and Circular Economy White Paper. Ellen MacArthur Foundation 16. April 2018. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/ce100/Water-and-Circular-Economy-White-paper-WIP-2018-04-13.pdf>
- Essential Services Commission, 2012, Review of Water Performance Report Indicators – Staff Discussion Paper,
- Eurocities, 2020. Circular Economy Action Plan. Speeding up the green transition of the EU's economy.
- European Commission (Ed.), 2001. Towards a local sustainability profile: European common indicators. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Luxembourg.
- European Commission., 2015. Communication No. 614, 2015. Closing the loop—an EU action plan for the circular economy
- European Commission., 2021. Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. https://ec.europa.eu/clima/sites/clima/files/adaptation/what/docs/eu_strategy_2021.pdf
- European Union, 2020. Taxonomy Report. Technical Annex. EU Technical Expert Group on Sustainable Finance, March
- Fekete, A., Sandholz, S., 2021. Here Comes the Flood, but Not Failure? Lessons to Learn after the Heavy Rain and Pluvial Floods in Germany 2021. *Water* 13, 3016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13213016>
- Forum for the future, 2010. The sustainable cities index. Ranking the 20 largest British cities. http://www.forumforthefuture.org/files/Sustainable_Cities_Index_2010_FINAL_15-10-10.pdf. Accessed 20 February 2011
- Gralepois, M., 2020. What Can We Learn from Planning Instruments in Flood Prevention? Comparative Illustration to Highlight the Challenges of Governance in Europe. *Water* 12, 1841. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12061841>.

- Gibberd, J., 2017. Smart cities, 2017. Water Resilience in Urban Areas, proceeding 11th Built Environment. Durban, South Africa.
- Giffender, R., Fertner, C., Kramar, H., Kalasek, R., Pichler-Milanovic, N., Meijers, E., 2007. Smart cities, ranking of European medium-sized cities. Central of regional science- Vienna UT
- Heinrichs, H., Martens, P., Michelsen, G., Wiek, A. (Eds.), 2016. Sustainability Science. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-7242-6>
- Jensen, O., Wu, H., 2018. Urban water security indicators: Development and pilot. Environ. Sci. Policy 83, 33–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.02.003>
- Johannessen, Å., Wamsler, C., 2017. What does resilience mean for urban water services? Ecology and Society 22. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08870-220101>
- Jongman, B., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Feyen, L., Aerts, J.C.J.H., Mechler, R., Botzen, W.J.W., Bouwer, L.M., Pflug, G., Rojas, R., Ward, P.J., 2014. Increasing stress on disaster-risk finance due to large floods. Nat. Clim. Change 4, 264–268. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2124>
- Jung, D., Kang, D., Kim, J.H., Lansey, K., 2014. Robustness-based design of water distribution systems. Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management 140(11).
- Koop, S.H.A., van Leeuwen, C.J., 2017. The challenges of water, waste, and climate change in cities. Environ. Dev. Sustain. 19, 385–418. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-016-9760-4>
- Koop, S.H.A., van Leeuwen, C.J., 2015. Assessment of the Sustainability of Water Resources Management: A Critical Review of the City Blueprint Approach. Water Resource Management. 29, 5649–5670. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-015-1139-z>
- Lehtonen, M., 2015. Indicators: tools for informing, monitoring or controlling? in: The Tools of Policy Formulation. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Ligtvoet, W., Hilderink, H. (Eds.), 2014. Towards a world of cities in 2050: an outlook on water related challenges: Background report to the UN-Habitat Global Report. PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, The Hague.
- Makropoulos, C., Nikolopoulos, D., Palmen, L., Kools, S., Segrave, A., Vries, D., Koop, S., Alphen, H.J. van, Vonk, E., Thienen, P. van, Rozos, E., Medema, G., 2018. A resilience assessment method for urban water systems. Urban Water J. 15, 316–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2018.1457166>
- Manaberi, M., Muthanna, T., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., 2021. Report on the planning and design phase in work package 2 (Milestone 10), B-WaterSmart.
- McGrane, S.J., Acuto M., Artioli, F., Chen, P.Y., Comber, R., Cottee, J., Farr-Wharton, G., Green, N., Helfgott, A., Larcom, S., McCann, J., O'Really, P., Salmoral, G., Scott, M., C.Todman, L., Van Gevelt, M., Yan, X., 2019. Scaling the nexus: Towards integrated frameworks for analysing water, energy and food. Geogr J. 185: 419– 431
- Mikovits, C., Rauch, W., Kleidorfer, M., 2018. Importance of scenario analysis in urban development for urban water infrastructure planning and management. Computers Environment and Urban System. 68, 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.09.006>
- Nilsen, V., Lier, J.A., Bjerkholt, J.T., Lindholm, O.G., 2011. Analysing urban floods and combined sewer overflows in a changing climate. Journal of Water and Climate. Change 2, 260–271. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2011.042>

Norman, E.S., Dunn, G., Bakker, K., Allen, D.M., Cavalcanti de Albuquerque, R., 2013. Water Security Assessment: Integrating Governance and Freshwater Indicators. *Water Resource Management*. 27, 535–551. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-012-0200-4>

Nottarp-Heim, D., Merkel, W., Alegre, H., Hein, A., gormley- gallagher, A., 2015. Transition to Sustainable Urban Water Services of Tomorrow: A handbook for policy makers, TRUST.

OECD, 2015. Water and Innovation for Green Growth, OECD Publishing, Paris. https://issuu.com/oecd.publishing/docs/water_and_innovation_for_green_grow/1?ff&e=3055080/12301119

Pellicer, S., Santa, G., Bleda, A.L., Maestre, R., Jara, A.J., Skarmeta, A.G., 2013. A Global Perspective of Smart Cities: A Survey, in 2013 Seventh International Conference on Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing. Presented at the 2013 Seventh International Conference on Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing, pp. 439–444. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IMIS.2013.79>

Picioara, I.-I., Eremia, M., Sănduleac, M., 2018. SMART CITY: Definition and Evaluation of Key Performance Indicators, in: 2018 International Conference and Exposition on Electrical And Power Engineering (EPE). Presented at the 2018 International Conference and Exposition on Electrical and Power Engineering (EPE), pp. 217–222. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEPE.2018.8559763>

Qi, J., Ba, Y., 2016. Smart City Construction Evaluation System Study Based on the Specialists Method and Analytic Hierarchy Process Method, in: 2016. Presented at the 2016 International Conference on Smart City and Systems Engineering (ICSCSE), pp. 149–152. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSCSE.2016.0049>

Reese, M., Gawel, E., 2018. Sustainable Urban Water Governance – Main Aims, Challenges and Institutional Approaches in Germany and Beyond, in: Kabisch, S., Koch, F., Gawel, E., Haase, A., Knapp, S., Krellenberg, K., Nivala, J., Zehnsdorf, A. (Eds.), *Urban Transformations: Sustainable Urban Development Through Resource Efficiency, Quality of Life and Resilience, Future City*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 145–171. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59324-1_9

Renouf, M.A., Serrao-Neumann, S., Kenway, S.J., Morgan, E.A., Low Choy, D., 2017. Urban water metabolism indicators derived from a water mass balance – Bridging the gap between visions and performance assessment of urban water resource management. *Water Res.* 122, 669–677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.05.060>

Schmuck, A., Wencki, K., 2021. Description and project planning for each Living Lab (Deliverable No. 1.7), B-WaterSmart.

Singh, S., Sharma, PK., Yoon. B., Shojafar, M., Cho, GH., Ra, I-H., 2020. Convergence of blockchain and artificial intelligence in IoT network for the sustainable smart city. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 63: 102364

Smith, D.J., 2017. Reliability, maintainability and risk: practical methods for engineers, Ninth edition. ed. Butterworth-Heinemann, an imprint of Elsevier, Kidlington, Oxford, United Kingdom.

Smol, M., Adam, C., Preisner, M., 2020. Circular economy model framework in the European water and wastewater sector. *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manag.* 22, 682–697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-019-00960-z>

Stavenhagen, M., Buurman, J., Tortajada, C., 2018. Saving water in cities: Assessing policies for residential water demand management in four cities in Europe. *Cities* 79, 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.03.008>

Stelzner, K., 2009. European Green City Index: Assessing the environmental impact of Europe's major cities. Siemens AG Corporate Communications and Government Affairs, Munich, Germany.

Ugarelli, R., Damman, S., Koop, S., Alegre, H., Cardoso, M.A., Almeida, M. do C., Oliveira, R., Vildåsen, S.S., Raspati, G., Barrero, M.J.A., Termes, M., Mateo, M.R., Schmuck, A., Strehl, C., Lekawska-Andrinopoulou, L., 2021. What is water-smartness and how to assess it? (Deliverable No. 6.1), B-WaterSmart.

UN-Habitat New Urban Agenda., 2017. Available online: <https://habitat3.org/the-new-urban-agenda/> accessed: November 2021.

United Nations University, 2013. Water security and the global water agenda: a UN-water analytical brief. United Nations University - Institute for Water, Environment and Health, Hamilton, Canada.

Van Leeuwen, C.J., Frijns, J., van Wezel, A., van de Ven, F.H.M., 2012. City Blueprints: 24 Indicators to Assess the Sustainability of the Urban Water Cycle. *Water Resour. Manag.* 26, 2177–2197. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-012-0009-1>

Van Leeuwen, C. J., 2013. City Blueprints: Baseline assessment of sustainable water management in 11 cities of the future. *Water Resources Management*, 27, 5191–5206.

Williams J (2019). Circular cities. *Urban Studies* 56: 2746–2762 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098018806133>